

Neuronal toxicity and recovery from early bortezomib-induced neuropathy: targeting the blood nerve barrier but not the dorsal root ganglion

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Extended methods

Behavioral testing

Animals were randomly assigned to the treatment groups. All experiments were performed by two researchers aware of the treatment group (1).

Mechanical hyperalgesia was examined using a series of von Frey filaments to record the withdrawal threshold of the hind paw (2). We used Dixon's up and down method to determine the 50% von Frey filament withdrawal threshold using the freely available up-down reader (3).

Thermal hyperalgesia was assessed performing the Hargreaves test with a thermal light stimulus. We measured the latency of withdrawal responses with an average from three trials. A recovery period of 10 min was kept and the cut-off latency set to 20 s to avoid any tissue damage (4).

Cold allodynia was measured using the cooling effect of acetone: one drop was applied onto the plantar surface of the hind paw (5). The response was recorded as a numerical score ranging from 0 to 3, where an increase in the numerical value represented a more exaggerated response of paw twitching and licking. An average of 3 consecutive measurements was recorded with 20-30 s intervals between measurements.

RNA isolation

RNA of the plantar skin and both sciatic nerves was harvested at the indicated time points, immediately shock frozen in liquid nitrogen, and stored then at -80°C. Total RNA was isolated using TRIzol® reagent (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany) (2) or QIAzol® Lysis reagent (Qiagen, #cat 79306) following vendor's instructions. RNA concentration and quality were determined using a spectrophotometer (Nandrop-2000, Fisher Scientific). We aimed an optical density quotient (OD 260/280) for follow-up experiments of 1.8 to 2.0.

Transcriptome analysis

RNA extracted from sciatic nerves and DRGs was used for bulk RNA sequencing. RNA quality was checked using a 2100 Bioanalyzer with the RNA 6000 Nano kit (Agilent Technologies). The RIN for all samples was ≥ 7.7 . DNA libraries suitable for sequencing were prepared from 300-500 ng of total RNA with oligo-dT capture beads for poly-A-mRNA enrichment using the TruSeq Stranded mRNA Library Preparation Kit (Illumina) according to manufacturer's instructions (1/2 volume). After 13-15 cycles of PCR amplification, the size distribution of the barcoded DNA libraries was estimated ~ 310 bp by electrophoresis on Agilent DNA 1000

Bioanalyzer microfluidic chips. Sequencing of pooled libraries, spiked with 1% PhiX control library, was performed at 21 to 41 million reads/sample in single-end mode with 100 nt read length on the NextSeq 2000 platform (Illumina). Demultiplexed FASTQ files were generated with bcl2fastq2 v2.20.0.422 or bcl-convert v4.0.3 (Illumina). Sequencing data are available at NCBI GEO (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo>). Raw sequencing reads were quality- and adapter-trimmed via Cutadapt (6) v2.5 using a cutoff Phred score of 20 in NextSeq mode, and reads without any remaining bases were discarded (parameters: --nextseq-trim=20 -m 1 -a AGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCAC). Processed reads were mapped to the rat genome (NCBI RefSeq assembly GCF_015227675.2/mRatBN7.2) using STAR (7) v2.7.2b with default parameters but including transcript annotations from RefSeq annotation version 108 for mRatBN7.2. This annotation was also used to generate read counts on exon level summarized for each gene via featureCounts v1.6.4 from the Subread package (8). Multi-mapping and multi-overlapping reads were counted strand-specific and reversely stranded with a fractional count for each alignment and overlapping feature (parameters: -s 2 -t exon -M -O --fraction). The count output was utilized to identify differentially expressed genes using DESeq2 (9)[1.24.0. Read counts were normalized by DESeq2 and fold-change shrinkage was conducted by setting the parameter betaPrior to TRUE. Differential expression was assumed at adjusted p-value after Benjamini-Hochberg correction (padj) < 0.05 and varying thresholds for log2FoldChange. Volcano plots were generated from DESeq2 results using the Bioconductor package EnhancedVolcano (10)version 1.2.0. Data are displayed in **Additional Table 1 and 2**.

String analysis

The interaction among differentially expressed genes (with a fold change of at least 1.5 and an adjusted p-val less than 0.05) was investigated using the STRING database (Ref added in the end). STRING uses text mining, experimental interactions, co-expression, neighborhood, gene-fusion, co-occurrence, and databases information to identify the interactions and calculation of interaction confidence score. Specifically, interactions with a high confidence score of 0.7 or higher were scrutinized, ensuring reliability of the interactions. For better and customized visualization, we imported the resulting networks in Cytoscape (Ref added in end). The disconnected genes were removed from the network and only largest connected cluster was considered for visualization. Proteins with shared function in relevant categories were clustered based on literature information. Expression data was mapped on network to visualize the upregulation or downregulation of cluster genes.

Reverse transcription quantitative PCR

RNA (1 µg, 500 ng for TJPs) was reverse transcribed to cDNA using the high-capacity cDNA reverse transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany) following manufacturer's instructions. Primers for RT-qPCR were designed by the Primer3 online data bank. For amplification we used the PowerUp™ SYBR® Green MasterMix (Applied Biosystems, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany) and the TaqMan detection system (2). Next, cDNA was amplified using the 7300 Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Darmstadt, Germany) with the following program for the SYBRGreen method: 95°C for 10 min and 40 cycles at 95°C for 3s and 60°C for 30s and for the TaqMan method: 95°C for 20 s and 45 cycles at 95°C for 1 s and 60 °C for 20 s *Gapdh* (nerve) and *Rlp13a* (skin) were used as a reference gen for quantification. Primer sequences and TaqMan probes are given in **Additional Table 3 and 4**. Relative abundances to *Gapdh/Rlp13a* were calculated by the ΔCt method (threshold cycle value). To compare samples from different groups the comparative cycle threshold ($\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}$) method was performed. So finally, mRNA expression was expressed as $2^{-\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}}$, standardized to a control condition (vehicle animals) set at 1.

Perineurial permeability assessment

To examine the perineurial permeability to small molecules, sciatic nerves were harvested and fixed for 1 h in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) followed by 15 min immersion in a 3% sodium fluorescein (NaFlu, molecular weight: 376 Da; Sigma Chemicals) in saline solution 2 ml of Evans blue albumin (EBA, 5% bovine albumin labelled with 1% Evans blue; molecular weight: 68 kDa, Sigma Chemicals) for 1 h (2). Finally, they were placed in sucrose 10% over night followed by embedding in Tissue-Tek O.C.T compound. After the first third of the

nerve was discarded by trimming, 10- μ m sections were cut and mounted on microscope cover glasses with permaFlour Mountant (Thermo Scientific).

Image analysis for barrier function

Images were blinded and randomized before being analyzed with the open-source program Fiji/ImageJ. Four RGB-8-bit TIF saved images per animal were used for fluorescence measurements. For perineural permeability, the whole endoneurium was manually defined as region of interest (ROI), whereas for Cldn1 fluorescence the whole perineurium was encircled. We calculated the fluorescence intensity (FI) by the subtraction of color intensity (average gray value) minus background signal (mean of color intensity of 3 background areas) (2). The means of four fascicles of each animal were then compared. For the quantification of Cldn1 cell-cell contacts, computational peak analysis was performed subtracting mean gray value*2.5 using the integrated Gaussian blur function ($r = 2$ pixel) (11). In total, five images per animal were analyzed. Intensity peaks were counted, after drawing a longitudinal line through the center of the perineurium and plotting their intensity maxima (= cell-cell contacts, settings: minimal peak amplitude = 1.5*standard deviation, minimal value of a maximum = 15, minimal peak distance = 1 μ m). Subsequently, the number of peaks was normalized to the perineural area and compared between groups.

Electrophysiological barrier characterization of the perineurial barrier: Dilution and bi-ionic potential measurements

Sciatic nerves were harvested and analyzed in modified Ussing chambers as described recently (Krug, Lee, Knobe et al., in preparation). In brief, sciatic nerves after preparation were placed in cold and gassed transport solution and were kept cooled during transport and preparation. After cleaning and opening the nerve, the inner endoneurial parts were carefully removed and the epiperineurial tissue pieces were mounted into modified Ussing chamber inserts, avoiding including thinned or branched areas.

In the Ussing chambers, voltage and transperineurial resistance (TER; R^t) were measured. Contribution of the bathing solution to the measured resistance was determined prior to each experiment and subtracted. Ussing chambers and water-jacketed gas lifts were filled with Ringer's solution (in mM: Na^+ 140; Cl^- 149.8; K^+ 5.4; Ca^{2+} 1.2; Mg^{2+} 1; HEPES 10; D(+)-glucose 10; D(+)-mannose 10.0; beta-hydroxybutyric acid 0.5; and L-glutamine 2.5 mmol/L; pH 7.4). The solution was equilibrated with 5% CO_2 and 95% O_2 at 37 °C.

Sodium and chloride permeabilities were determined from dilution potentials. For this, potential changes were recorded by switching the solution of one hemichamber to a solution containing a reduced concentration of NaCl, but with all other components identical to the standard Ringer's (osmolality was balanced by mannitol). The resulting dilution potentials were used for further calculations employing the and the Goldman-Hodgkin-Katz equation as described before (12). Potassium permeability was determined similar in bi-ionic potentials, where the solution in one hemichamber was changed to one in which part of the NaCl was replaced isoosmotically by the KCl.

For the measuring fluorescein fluxes, 5 μ L / 5 mL of fluorescein (100 mM) was added to one side of the tissue mounted into Ussing chambers, and samples (300 μ L) were collected and replaced 0, 10, 20, 30, and 40 min after addition from the other side. Tracer fluxes were determined from the collected samples by measuring the concentrations with a fluorometer at 520 nm (Tecan Infinite M200, Tecan, Switzerland).

Semithin sections

For semithin sections, sciatic nerve tissue was fixed in 4% PFA/2.5% glutaraldehyde in 0.1 M NaCaCo solution (pH 7.4). Nerves were postfixed in 2% osmium tetroxide, and embedded in plastic. Semithin sections (0.5 μ m) were prepared and stained with azure-methylene blue. Sections were visualized by brightfield microscopy (Biorevo BZ-9000-E, Keyence, Osaka, Japan), blinded and randomized before analysis. Images were processed with Fiji/ImageJ and a semi-automatic quantification tool (gratio.efil.de, Plugin v3.2, setup: 1 px \triangleq 0.17761 μ m). Nerve fiber density was measured by counting manually myelinated nerve fibers in a defined area of 10.000 μm^2 (one image/nerve and six animals/group). To evaluate the ratio of axon diameter to total fiber diameter (g-ratio), the plugin algorithm arbitrary marked fibers in the nerve, which were subsequently measured manually. The setup consisted of at least eight measurements per image and four images per

animal (n = 6). Measurements continued until at least two axon sizes per quartile were met. In addition, axon diameter as well as myelin area was calculated for fiber distribution studies, assuming nearly round fiber shapes.

Immunofluorescence microscopy and IENFD measurement

Harvested nerves were embedded in Tissue-Tek O.C.T compound and snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen. Samples were cryo-sectioned at 10 µm thickness and permeabilized with 0,5% Triton-X100 in PBS solution and blocked for 30 min with 3% bovine serum albumin and 1% goat serum in PBS solution. Antibodies are depicted in **Additional Table 5**.

Sections were incubated with the primary antibody mouse anti-Cldn1, rabbit anti-Cttn and mouse anti-Ntn1, overnight at 4°C (Suppl. Tab. 3). Washing on the next day was followed by incubation with the secondary antibody goat anti-mouse FITC. Nuclei were stained with DAPI 2 mg/ml in distilled water (Sigma-Aldrich, Ref D9542, 1:3000) for 10 min. Next, slides were rewashed and mounted with Aqua Poly/Mount (Polysciences Inc., Ref 18606). Sections were visualized by immunofluorescence microscopy (Bioevo BZ-9000-E, Keyence, Osaka, Japan) using the same settings for all samples. A higher image resolution was necessary for computational peak analysis, which we obtained by confocal microscopy (Fluoview1000, Olympus).

Skin was fixed in 4% PFA for 1 h and then placed in 10% sucrose overnight followed by Tissue-Tek O.C.T compound. The skin blocks were cryo-sectioned at 40 µm thickness. After 5 min of washing in PBS the skin sections were permeabilized and blocked for 1 h in a 10 % Donkey serum (Sigma Aldrich) and 0.3% Triton-X 100 (Sigma-Aldrich) in PBS solution.

Skin sections were cryo-sectioned at 40 µm thickness and incubated with either rabbit anti-Pgp9.5 and goat anti-collagen IV or mouse anti-Ntn1 antibody overnight at 4°C (Suppl. Tab. 3). On the following day the sections were washed and incubated to the corresponding secondary antibodies (Suppl. Tab. 3). Next, they were washed again and finally mounted with (Sigma-Aldrich, Ref D9542, 1:3000). Sections were viewed by immunofluorescence microscopy (Axio Imager.M2, Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany).

Patient cohort

Patients were recruited at the Multiple Myeloma Centre of the Department of Internal Medicine II at the University Hospital Würzburg and are part of a larger monocentric, non-randomized, observational clinical trial (DRKS00025422) (13). All patients underwent a standardized neurological examination and including the Overall Disability Sum Score (ODSS), the modified Toronto Clinical Neuropathy Score (mTCNS) and the Neuropathic Pain Symptom Inventory (NPSI). Nerve conduction studies (NCS) were done on the right sural, median, and tibial nerves following standard procedures and a standardized skin biopsy was taken at the calf and thigh. Only patients with painful BIPN [pain average 2.0 (range 1-6) on the numerical pain scale (0-no pain; 10-worst pain)] were included in the analysis.

Skin punch biopsy and gene expression

Skin punch biopsy (6 mm; device by Stiefel GmbH, Offenbach, Germany) were taken in local anesthesia from the distal lateral calf according to a published protocol (Üçeyler N, Kafke W, Riediger N, He L, Necula G, Toyka KV, Sommer C (2010) Elevated proinflammatory cytokine expression in affected skin in small fiber neuropathy. *Neurology* 74:1806–1813). Skin was stored in 500µl RNeasy Protect tissue reagent (QIAGEN GmbH, Hilden, Germany) over night at 4 °C. The next day, the reagent was removed and stored at -80 °C until further processing for gene expression analysis.

The miRNeasy Micro Kit® (QIAGEN GmbH, Hilden, Germany) was used. The samples were thawed on ice and immersed in QIAzol Lysis reagent® (QIAGEN GmbH, Hilden, Germany) using a Micra homogenizer (ART Prozess und Labortechnik, Germany) followed by incubation (room temperature (RT), 5 min). 140 µl chloroform (laboratory production of ultimate elements) was added, shaken vigorously for 15s and incubated again at RT for 2-3 minutes followed by centrifugation (12000g, 15 min, 4 °C). The upper aqueous phase was transferred to a new collection tube and mixed with 525 µl 100% Ethanol (Merck KGAA, Darmstadt, Germany). 700 µl were pipetted into RNeasy MinElute spin column in a 2 ml collection tube, centrifuged

(8000g for 15 s at RT) and flow-through was discarded. This step was repeated until all of remain sample was used. 700 μ l Buffer RWT was added to the RNeasy MinElute spin column, centrifuged (15 s at \geq 8000 x g) and the flow-through discarded. 500 μ l Buffer RPE were added onto the RNeasy MinElute spin column, centrifuged (15 s at 8000g) and flow-through was discarded. Next, 500 μ l of 80% Ethanol (Merck KGAA, Darmstadt, Germany) was added to the RNeasy MinElute spin column, centrifuged (2 min at 8000g), flow-through and collection tube was discarded. RNeasy MinElute spin column was placed in a new 2 ml collection tube, centrifuged at full speed for 5 min at RT, flow-through and collection tube was discarded. RNeasy MinElute spin column was placed in a new 1.5 ml collection tube, 14 μ l RNase-free water was added directly to the center of the spin column membrane and centrifuged for 1 min at full speed to elute the RNA. After the RNA quality and quantity was assessed with a NanoDrop™ One (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), the samples were stored at -80 °C.

All used cyclers and PCR reagents were purchased from Applied Biosystems (Darmstadt, Germany). For reverse transcription of the obtained mRNA to cDNA, 250 ng of mRNA and TaqMan Reverse Transcription Reagents® were applied in a total volume of 100 μ l. The following components were included: 10 μ l 10 \times PCR, buffer, 22 μ l MgCl₂, 20 μ l dNTP, 5 μ l random hexamer, 2 μ l RNase inhibitor, 6.25 μ l multiscribe reverse transcriptase. Following PCR cycler conditions were used: annealing (25 °C, 10 min), reverse transcription (37 °C, 60 min), and enzyme inactivation (95 °C, 5 min).

TaqMan Master Mix® and 3.5 μ l of sample cDNA were used for real-time qPCR performed in a StepOnePlus™ Cycler. RPL13A (Assay-ID: Hs04194366_g1 VIC-MGB, Applied Biosystems; Darmstadt, Germany), was used as endogenous control. The real-time qPCRs contained 5 μ l TaqMan Advanced Master Mix, 0.5 μ l TaqMan Assay RPL13A (Assay-ID: Hs04194366_g1 VIC-MGB, Applied Biosystems; Darmstadt, Germany), 0.5 μ l of TaqMan Assay Netrin 1 (Assay-ID: Netrin 1 Hs00924151_m1 FAM-MGB, Applied Biosystems; Darmstadt, Germany) and 0.5 μ l nuclease free water in a total volume of 6.5 μ l. Following PCR cycler conditions were used: incubation (2 min, 50 °C), second incubation (95 °C, 2 min), 40 cycles (3 s, 95 °C and 30 s, 60 °C). We investigated gene expression of Netrin 1 (Assay-ID: Netrin 1 Hs00924151_m1 FAM-MGB, Applied Biosystems; Darmstadt, Germany)

Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were done using Graph Pad version 9 software. Given the low number of animals, we used the non-parametric Mann-Whitney-U-test or unpaired t-test for parametric data. For behavioral test analysis, we performed the non-parametric Friedman test RM with Dunn's *post-hoc* test. Nonlinear regression was proceeded by the Extra sum-of-squares F test, comparing the best-fitting equation models of all datasets. Differences between groups were considered significant if $p < 0.05$. All data are expressed as mean \pm SEM or median \pm error.

Additional tables and figures

Gene	12 d	18 d	Expression in				
			Schwann cells	epineurial cells	perineurial cells	immune cells	endothelial cells
<i>Nr1d1</i>	↑↑	↓	+	++++	++++	+	++++
<i>Dbp</i>	↑↑	↓↓↓	+	++	++	++	+++
<i>Cldn11</i>	↑↑	↓↓↓	+	+	-++	-	+
<i>Rph3al</i>	↑	↓	-	-	-	+++	-
<i>Myh7</i>	↑	↓	-	+	+	+++	+
<i>Htra1</i>	↑	↓	-	+	+	+++	-
<i>Mobp</i>	↑	↓	+	++++	+++	+	+
<i>Per2</i>	↑	↓	+	++++	+++	+	+
<i>Fkbp5</i>	↑		-	+	+	-	-
<i>Myh7b</i>	↑	↓	-	-	-	+++	-
<i>Htr3a</i>	↑	↓	-	++++	++++	++	-
<i>Zbtb16</i>	↑		-	-	-	-	++
<i>Lypd1</i>	↑		-	++++	+++	-	+
<i>Slc24a2</i>	↑		-	++	+++	-	+++
<i>Ryr3</i>	↑		-	++++	++	+	+
<i>Ciart</i>	↑	↓↓↓	-	-	+++	-	-
<i>Galnt15</i>	↑	↓	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Htra1</i>	↑	↓	-	-	+++	-	-
<i>Ddn</i>	↑	↓	-	-	+++	-	-
<i>Fxyd7</i>	↑	↓	-	+++	++++	-	-
<i>Faah</i>	↑	↓	-	+++	+++	-	-
<i>Lrg1</i>	↑	↓	-	-	+	-	-
<i>Gstp1</i>	↑	↓	-	++	++++	-	+
<i>Bhlhe41</i>	↑	↓	-	+++	+++	-	++
<i>Ttll9</i>	↑	↓	-	++++	+++	-	-
<i>Hmgcs2</i>	↑	↓	-	-	+++	-	-
<i>Ca14</i>	↑	↓	-	+	+++	-	+
<i>Rap1gap</i>	↑	↓	+	++++	++++	+	+
<i>Cpt1a</i>	↑	↓	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Arhgef3</i>	↑	↓	-	-	+	-	-
<i>Pebp1</i>	↑	↓	-	-	+++	-	-
<i>Acaa1a</i>		↓	-	-	+	-	-
<i>Kcnp2</i>		↓	+	+++	+++	++	+
<i>Smoc1</i>		↓	-	-	+++	-	-
<i>Abcg2</i>		↓	-	+++	++++	-	-
<i>Mpped1</i>		↓	-	++	+++	-	-
<i>Serpinb6b</i>		↓	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Slc26a8</i>		↓	-	+	+++	-	-
<i>Mt3</i>		↓	-	+	++++	-	-
<i>Slc19a3</i>		↓	-	-	+++	-	-
<i>Acaa1b</i>		↓	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Rrad</i>		↓	-	+	+	-	-

Additional Table 1 Top genes upregulated at maximum hypersensitivity (12 d) and their recovery during pain resolution (18 d). Location in the sciatic nerve according to the murine sciatic nerve atlas. ↓↓ Log2change <-1, ↑↑ Log2change >1, ↓ Log2change between <-1 and 0, ↑ Log2change between <1 and 0. + slightly, ++ moderately, +++ and ++++ highly, and – not expressed in cells in the sciatic nerve (14).

Gene	12 d	18 d	Expression in				
			Schwann cells	epineurial cells	perineurial cells	immune cells	endothelial cells
<i>Clec11a</i>	↓↓	↑	-	+++	+++	-	-
<i>Fcgr2a</i>	↓↓	↑	-	-	-	+++	-
<i>Csf2rb</i>	↓↓	↑	-	-	-	++	+++
<i>Lyve1</i>	↓↓	↑	-	+	+	+++	+
<i>Thy1</i>	↓↓	↑	-	++++	++	+	+
<i>Olfm1</i>	↓	↑	+	++++	+++	+	+
<i>Tgm2</i>	↓	↑	-	++	+++	-	+++
<i>Fcna</i>	↓	↑	-	-	-	+++	-
<i>Lum</i>	↓	↑	+	++++	+++	+	+
<i>Srpx2</i>	↓		-	++++	+++	-	+
<i>Itgax</i>	↓	↑	-	+	++++	-	-
<i>Plxdc1</i>	↓	↑	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Adgre1</i>	↓	↑	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Qpct</i>	↓	↑	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Rac2</i>	↓	↑	+	+++	+++	+	++++
<i>Siglec5</i>	↓	↑	-	++	++	+	+
<i>Npas2</i>	↓	↑↑	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Medag</i>	↓	↑↑	+	++++	+++	-	-
<i>Cpa3</i>	↓	↑↑	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Clmp</i>	↓	↑↑	-	++++	++++	-	-
<i>Hcn4</i>		↑↑	+	++	+++	+	++++
<i>Cyp2s1</i>		↑↑	+	-	-	-	-
<i>Col6a5</i>		↑↑	+	+	-	-	+
<i>Krt19</i>		↑↑	-	+++	+	-	+++
<i>Cpxm2</i>		↑↑	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Clstn3</i>		↑↑	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
<i>Mettl7b</i>		↑↑	+	+	++++	+	+
<i>Ntn1</i>		↑↑	+	++++	++++	+	+
<i>Klf5</i>		↑↑	+	++++	++++	+	+
<i>Papln</i>		↑↑	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Adora1</i>		↑↑	-	-	++	-	-
<i>Nrxn2</i>		↑↑	-	-	-	-	++
<i>Wwc1</i>		↑↑	-	-	++	-	-
<i>Fras1</i>		↑↑	-	+	++	-	-
<i>Slc6a20</i>		↑↑	-	-	++	-	-
<i>Boc</i>		↑↑	-	+++	+++	-	-
<i>Lad1</i>		↑↑	-	-	++	-	-
<i>Mpzl2</i>		↑↑	-	+	++++	-	-

Additional Table 2 Top genes downregulated at maximum hypersensitivity (12 d) and their recovery during resolution (18 d). Location in the sciatic nerve according to the murine sciatic nerve atlas. ↓↓ Log2change <-1, ↑↑ Log2change >1, ↓ Log2change between <-1 and 0, ↑ Log2change between <1 and 0. + slightly, ++ moderately, +++ and +++ highly, and – not expressed in cells in the sciatic nerve (14).

Gene	Company	Number
<i>Gapdh</i>	ThermoFisher Scientific	Rn01462662_g1
<i>Cldn1</i>	ThermoFisher Scientific	Rn00581740_m1
<i>Cldn5</i>	ThermoFisher Scientific	Rn01753146_s1
<i>Cldn19</i>	ThermoFisher Scientific	Rn01416537_m1
<i>Ocln</i>	ThermoFisher Scientific	Rn00580064_m1
<i>Tjp1</i>	ThermoFisher Scientific	Rn02116071_s1
<i>Il1b</i>	ThermoFisher Scientific	Rn00580432_g1
<i>Il6</i>	ThermoFisher Scientific	Rn01410330_g1
<i>Tnfa</i> (LOC103694)	ThermoFisher Scientific	Rn99999017_m1
<i>Il10</i>	ThermoFisher Scientific	Rn01483988_g1
<i>Mbp</i>	ThermoFisher Scientific	Rn01399619_m1

Additional Table 3 TaqMan-Primers for qPCR

Gene	Forward	Reverse
<i>Gapdh</i>	5'-AGTCTACTGGCGTCTTCAC-3'	5'-TCATATTTCTCGTGGTTCAC-3'
<i>Rlp13a</i>	5'-TCTCCGAAAGCGGATGAACAC-3'	5'-CAACACCTTGAGGCGTTCCA-3'
<i>Ctnn</i>	5'-CTCTCCAAGCACTGCTCACA-3'	5'-CGGTCAGCTTGCACTCCATA-3'
<i>Ntn1</i>	5'-CAGGAAGGACTATGCTGTCCA-3'	5'-TACGACTTGCGCCTGCTTG-3'
<i>Unc5b</i>	5'-CGACCCTAAAAGCCGCCCC-3'	5'-GGGATCTTGTCGGCAGAGTCC-3'
<i>Neo1</i>	5'-TGTGATGGTGACCAAAGGCA-3'	5'-GGAGGCTGCCAGTTCATT-3'

Additional Table 4 Primer sequences for qPCR

Antibody name	Target	Vendor	Host organism	Antibody ID
Anti-Cldn1 monoclonal antibody (2H10D10)	Cldn1 canine, human, mouse, rat	Thermo Fisher	mouse	AB_2533323
Protein Gene Product 9.5 (PGP9.5, UCHL1)	PGP9.5 human, rat	Zytomed Systems	rabbit	ZYT-516-3344
Anti-type IV collagen-UNLB polyclonal antibody	Collagen IV human, rat	Southern Biotech	goat	AB_2721907
Anti-Ctnn polyclonal antibody	Ctnn human, mouse, rat	Thermo Fisher	rabbit	AB_2544610
Anti-mouse netrin-1 antibody	Ntn1 mouse, rat	RD-Systems	rat	MAB1109
Anti-mouse IgG FITC polyclonal antibody	Mouse IgG	Sigma-Aldrich	goat	AB_259378
Donkey anti-goat IgG (H+L) cross-adsorbed secondary antibody, Alexa Fluor™ 488	Goat IgG	Thermo Fischer	donkey	AB_2534102
Donkey anti-rabbit IgG (H+L) highly cross-adsorbed secondary antibody, Alexa Fluor™ 555	Rabbit IgG	Thermo Fischer	donkey	AB_162543
Goat anti-rat IgG (H+L) cross-adsorbed secondary antibody, Alexa Fluor™ 594	Rat IgG	Thermo Fischer	goat	AB_10561522

Additional Table 5 Antibodies for immunohistochemistry

Additional Figure 1: Pathway analysis in the sciatic nerve in BIPN. Wistar rats were treated with one cycle of BTZ, nerves harvested at 12 (hyperalgesia) and 18 d (resolution) and their transcriptome analyzed. **(a, b)** GO Term analysis of up- and downregulated genes comparing. $n = 3/\text{group}$

Additional Figure 2: Less network changes in DRGs in pain resolution. DRGs were harvested at the time point of maximum hyperalgesia (BTZ_12d) and pain resolution (BTZ_18d). No changes were found at maximum hyperalgesia compared to vehicle control. (a) Volcano plots depict up- and downregulated genes for pain resolution comparing BTZ_18d with BTZ_12d. (b, c) Pathway and network analysis of downregulated genes. $n = 6$.

Additional Figure 3: Transient BNB breakdown and resealing for small molecules in BIPN, but no change in classical tight junction proteins. Male Wistar rats were 4 times injected i.p. with 0,2 mg/kg BTZ (blue datapoints) similar to one cycle in patients; control animals were treated with solvent (grey, Veh). (a, b) Endoneurial permeability for Evans blue albumin (EBA, 69 kDa) quantified by measuring fluorescence intensity/area. Dashed line depicts the inner border of the perineurium P (E = Endoneurium). Scale bars = 200 μ m. All datapoints represent mean \pm SEM. Unpaired t-test, ($n = 6$), * $p < 0.05$. (c-f) Relative mRNA expression of different TJPs in the sciatic nerve. Unpaired t-test, Mann-Whitney-U-Test. Graphs show mean \pm SEM or median and interquartile range, ($n = 5 - 6$), * $p < 0.05$ (g-i) Immunoreactivity for Cldn1 and quantification in the perineurium (fluorescence intensity/area), Unpaired t-test for comparison and Semiquantitative analysis of Cldn1 intensity peaks in the perineurium. Arrows point at Cldn1 stripe-like structure. E = endoneurium, P = perineurium. Scale bars = 25 μ m. ($n = 6$).

Additional Figure 4: Restored blood-nerve-barrier after complete recovery of BIPN. Wistar rats were treated with BTZ for one cycle and the nerve harvested after 25 d. Perineurial permeability after ex vivo incubation with fluorescein (Fluo, 330 Da). Scale bar = 200 μ m.

Additional Figure 5: Relative mRNA expression of Ntn1 receptors in nerve and skin. Rats were treated with on cycle of BTZ and nerve (a, b) or skin tissue (c, d) taken at indicated time points All datapoints represent mean \pm SEM, n = 5-6. $p > 0.05$, two-way ANOVA, Bonferroni post hoc test for multiple comparisons.

References

- Zumbusch AS, McEachern ELF, Morgan OB, Nickner E, Mogil JS. Normative Preclinical Algesiometry Data on the von Frey and Radiant Heat Paw-Withdrawal Tests: An Analysis of Data from More Than 8,000 Mice Over 20 Years. *J Pain*. 2024 Jan 12. Epub 20240112. doi:10.1016/j.jpain.2024.01.333. Cited in: Pubmed; PMID 38219851.
- Ben-Kraiem A, Sauer RS, Norwig C, Popp M, Bettenhausen AL, Atalla MS, Brack A, Blum R, Doppler K, Rittner HL. Selective blood-nerve barrier leakiness with claudin-1 and vessel-associated macrophage loss in diabetic polyneuropathy. *J Mol Med (Berl)*. 2021 Sep;99(9):1237-1250. Epub 20210521. doi:10.1007/s00109-021-02091-1. Cited in: Pubmed; PMID 34018017.

3. Gonzalez-Cano R, Boivin B, Bullock D, Cornelissen L, Andrews N, Costigan M. Up-Down Reader: An Open Source Program for Efficiently Processing 50% von Frey Thresholds. *Front Pharmacol.* 2018;9:433. Epub 20180501. doi:10.3389/fphar.2018.00433. Cited in: Pubmed; PMID 29765323.
4. Chen JT, Schmidt L, Schurger C, Hankir MK, Krug SM, Rittner HL. Netrin-1 as a Multitarget Barrier Stabilizer in the Peripheral Nerve after Injury. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2021 Sep 18;22(18). Epub 20210918. doi:10.3390/ijms221810090. Cited in: Pubmed; PMID 34576252.
5. Yoon C, Wook YY, Sik NH, Ho KS, Mo CJ. Behavioral signs of ongoing pain and cold allodynia in a rat model of neuropathic pain. *Pain.* 1994 Dec;59(3):369-376. doi:10.1016/0304-3959(94)90023-X. Cited in: Pubmed; PMID 7708411.
6. Martin M. Cutadapt removes adapter sequences from high-throughput sequencing reads. *EMBnetjourna.* 2011;17:3. doi:10.14806/ej.17.1.200.
7. Dobin A, Davis CA, Schlesinger F, Drenkow J, Zaleski C, Jha S, Batut P, Chaisson M, Gingeras TR. STAR: ultrafast universal RNA-seq aligner. *Bioinformatics.* 2013 Jan 1;29(1):15-21. Epub 20121025. doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/bts635. Cited in: Pubmed; PMID 23104886.
8. Liao Y, Smyth GK, Shi W. featureCounts: an efficient general purpose program for assigning sequence reads to genomic features. *Bioinformatics.* 2014 Apr 1;30(7):923-30. Epub 20131113. doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/btt656. Cited in: Pubmed; PMID 24227677.
9. Love MI, Huber W, Anders S. Moderated estimation of fold change and dispersion for RNA-seq data with DESeq2. *Genome Biol.* 2014;15(12):550. doi:10.1186/s13059-014-0550-8. Cited in: Pubmed; PMID 25516281.
10. Blighe KS, Rana S, Lewis M. EnhancedVolcano: Publication-ready volcano plots with enhanced colouring and labeling. 2018. doi:<https://github.com/kevinblighe/EnhancedVolcano>.
11. Reinhold AK, Schwabe J, Lux TJ, Salvador E, Rittner HL. Quantitative and Microstructural Changes of the Blood-Nerve Barrier in Peripheral Neuropathy. *Front Neurosci.* 2018;12:936. Epub 20181218. doi:10.3389/fnins.2018.00936. Cited in: Pubmed; PMID 30618565.
12. Gunzel D, Stuver M, Kausalya PJ, Haisch L, Krug SM, Rosenthal R, Meij IC, Hunziker W, Fromm M, Muller D. Claudin-10 exists in six alternatively spliced isoforms that exhibit distinct localization and function. *J Cell Sci.* 2009 May 15;122(Pt 10):1507-17. Epub 20090421. doi:10.1242/jcs.040113. Cited in: Pubmed; PMID 19383724.
13. Cebulla N, Schirmer D, Runau E, Flamm L, Gommersbach S, Stengel H, Zhou X, Einsele H, Reinhold AK, Rogalla von Bieberstein B, Zeller D, Rittner H, Kortum KM, Sommer C. Neurofilament light chain levels indicate acute axonal damage under bortezomib treatment. *J Neurol.* 2023 Jun;270(6):2997-3007. Epub 20230218. doi:10.1007/s00415-023-11624-2. Cited in: Pubmed; PMID 36802032.
14. Gerber D, Pereira JA, Gerber J, Tan G, Dimitrieva S, Yanguéz E, Suter U. Transcriptional profiling of mouse peripheral nerves to the single-cell level to build a sciatic nerve ATlas (SNAT). *Elife.* 2021 Apr 23;10. Epub 20210423. doi:10.7554/eLife.58591. Cited in: Pubmed; PMID 33890853.